

STADIEM

STARTUP DRIVEN INNOVATION IN EUROPEAN MEDIA

D1.6 COMMUNITY BUILDING ACTIVITY REPORT

version 2

Revision: v.1.0

Work package	WP 1
Task	Task 1.1 and Task 1.4
Due date	30/09/2022
Submission date	31/12/2022
Deliverable lead	VRT
Version	1.0
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Grant Agreement No.: 957321
Call: H2020-ICT-2018-2020
Topic: ICT-44-2020
Type of action: IA

Abstract	The deliverable provides an overview of the community building activities the STADIEM consortium organised or participated in during year 2 (October 2021-September 2022) of the project. It relates to D1.1 (Community Building Strategy), D1.3 (Community map and database v2) and builds upon D1.5 (Community
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	building activity report v1) that describes the activities for year 1. This deliverable details for each group of stakeholders the community building activity in accordance with their level of engagement towards STADIEM: 1) inform, 2) convince and 3) engage. It presents in the conclusion some operational lessons learned as well as, based on the results from the previous chapter, the future direction of this task.
Keywords	Community building strategy, community management, community engagement, stakeholders, community building activities

Document Revision History

Version	Date	Description of change	List of contributor(s)
v.0.1	15/09/2022	First draft shared with partners	Wim Vanobberghen (VRT)
v.0.2	15/10/2022	input provided by partners	Mathias Teuwen (VRT), Marianne Fjellhaug (MCB), Galileo Disperati (Martel), Lina Silveira (F6S)
v0.3	30/10/2022	2nd draft shared with partners based on input 15/10/2022	Wim Vanobberghen (VRT)
v0.4	30/11/2022	Input provided by EBU, STK & NMA	Merlene Vrielmann (NMA), Tiphaine Vigniel (STK) & Carmela Asero (EBU)
v0.5	21/12/2022	Final draft shared with partners and internal review by STK	Sten Saluveer (STK)
v0.6	23/12/2022	incorporating comments internal reviewer	Wim Vanobberghen (VRT)
V1.0	31/12/2022	Final version for submission to EC	Wim Vanobberghen (VRT)

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Dissemination Level		
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CL	Classified, information as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC	

CO	Confidential to STADIEM project and Commission Services	
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* R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)

DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs

DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.

OTHER: Software, technical diagram, etc.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

STADIEM is the first pan-European accelerator and start-up-to-corporate supplier program focusing on scaling of NGM (Next Generation Media) solutions through a co-creation and piloting program between innovative start-ups/scale-ups and European (media) corporates. Given this objective, it will be crucial for the program's success to rely not only on the establishment of a well-functioning community of its four hubs (NMA, VRT, STK, MCB), but also to make fruitful connections with other relevant ecosystems and actors in the EU in order to generate a cross-fertilization. STADIEM can benefit from experiences, stakeholders and benefits from other hubs and networks, while these actors in return can learn from the activities, experiences and best practices from the STADIEM program and projects.

This report provides an overview of the community building activities that the STADIEM consortium organised or participated in during the second year of the project, from October 2021 to September 2022.

These activities were based on the Community Building Strategy (see D1.1 '*Community Building Strategy*') and the Community Map and Database (see D2.1 '*Community map and database*' v2) and built on two main insights from the first-year report on community building (see D1.5 '*Community Building Activity Report*' v1):

- A need to increase STADIEM's physical presence in the hubs and the wider European media technology scene, especially after Covid-19 restrictions were lifted;
- And the need to intensify the activities in a year when the project had two open call cohort running at the same time.

The report presents that STADIEM met all the KPIs to measure the success of its community building activities and reached its three main stakeholder groups:

- Stakeholders who need to be informed about the project;
- Stakeholders who need to be convinced of the value of the project and contribute to it in specific ways;
- And stakeholders who need to be actively engaged in the project activities.

The first group is reached mainly through communication and dissemination actions by the project and consortium partners, while the second and third groups are reached through targeted communication, encounters, and events of various sizes and formats to build the STADIEM ecosystem and engage them in the STADIEM community.

Compared to the first year, the main achievements of the second year include:

- An increase in communication output (videos, social media posts, word-of-mouth campaigns) and its reach; invitations for STADIEM partners to attend and participate in events;
- An increase in targeted publications to stakeholders;
- A wider geographical coverage of open call participants and community building efforts;
- The organisation of STADIEM's own events at major international or regional events showcasing STADIEM beneficiaries or bringing stakeholders together around a specific issue;
- And the facilitation of project-related events where STADIEM enabled or endorsed directly or indirectly pitching for start-ups, engaged corporate partners from the hub networks, or facilitated the presence of start-ups at other events.

During this period the consortium learned that a combination of online and physical presence is essential for community building activities but finding the right balance between the two depends on the specific context.

While online activities are useful for raising awareness about the project and making initial connections between actors, physical events are important for deepening relationships and interactions between actors in the ecosystem or generating word-of-mouth effects, both in formal settings (such as events or panel participations) and informal settings (such as happy hours). In this way, two-way exchange between the program and project and the ecosystem can take place, leading to a more dynamic and interactive community.

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1. INTRODUCTION

This document presents an overview of the community building activities that the STADIEM consortium organised or participated in during the second year of the project (October 2021 to September 2022). These activities are based on the tasks T1.1 "Community Building Strategy", T1.2 "Ecosystem Mapping" and T1.3 "Opportunity Spotting" carried out during this period of time. The report is based on the conclusions of the Deliverable D1.5 "Community Building Activity Report v1", which covered the STADIEM community building activities for the first year of the project (October 2021 to September 2022). The main outcome of that report was that there was no need to update the initial community building strategy outlined in D1.1 "Community Building Strategy".

The report is structured into five chapters:

- Chapter 2 provides the key elements of the community building strategy as background information to understand the overview of the activities and monitoring in the second year of STADIEM.
- Chapters 3, 4, and 5 provide an overview of the activities for each of the three stakeholder groups identified by their level of engagement: inform (Chapter 3), convince (Chapter 4), and engage (Chapter 5).
- Based on a monitoring of the activities compared to the KPIs set for each of these three groups, the report concludes in Chapter 6 with the main insights and an outlook for the third year of the STADIEM project.

Finally, the Annex section includes a list of videos by the project and the project partners as well as an overview of social media posts and target publications by the project partners other than the project communications. Where possible, a link to the online material is provided.

2. KEY ELEMENTS OF STADIEM'S COMMUNITY BUILDING STRATEGY

Main groups of Stakeholders

The STADIEM project has identified three main groups of stakeholders in its ecosystem: inform, convince, and engage.

Each group has a specific value for the STADIEM project and can also benefit from STADIEM activities and outcomes. Also, each group requires a specific level of engagement and specific tactics for engagement.

The inform group consists of cultural/artistic organisations, sectors/verticals unrelated to the media industry, standardisation bodies/initiatives, users/audience/civil society, and public authorities/regulators/policy makers.

The convince group consists of non-media sectors/verticals related to the media industry, media producers, traditional media, operators, and researchers in industry and academia/education.

The engage group consists of tech innovators, incubators and accelerators, investors, corporates, and start-ups, scale-ups, and SMEs in media tech.

Detailed information about these stakeholders can be found in D1.3 "Community Map and Database v2".

Impact of Covid-19 restriction measures

The STADIEM project's community building activities continued to be affected by Covid-19 restrictions in Europe during the second year of the project. Physical events were not able to be held or were cancelled. The restrictions began to ease in June 2022, but due to summer holidays in July and August, only one month of the second year was relatively unaffected by Covid-19. Despite these challenges, the project continued to explore digital opportunities and build on the experiences of the first year as well as the consortium members attended physical events as much as possible.

Assessing performance and KPI's

STADIEM uses **the traffic light model** to monitor the extent to which a KPI is reached within the second year of the project. The same interpretation as for the previous report was used in this report.

KPI met or exceeded
Slightly underperforming
Underperforming /Covid-19 impact

3. INFORM

In order to inform various stakeholders about the STADIEM project and its outcomes and create awareness about STADIEM, the communication activities of the project were carried out in WP5 and led by Martel Innovate.

These activities were increased in output and reach compared to the first year of the project ((September 2021 - September 2022) and included the use of various online channels as well as word-of-mouth campaigns at events attended by partners.

Additionally, the STADIEM consortium partners individually created and shared their own videos and social media posts to amplify the project's work and outcomes. A list of relevant videos and social media posts can be found in Annex I and Annex II of this deliverable.

One point of attention for the final year of STADIEM is to continue increasing the number of followers on Twitter, although it may be the case that followers do not feel the need to follow the STADIEM social pages if they are already seeing the posts being shared by partners. The same may be true for views on the STADIEM YouTube channel.

TABLE 1: OVERVIEW OF THE COMMUNITY BUILDING ACTIVITIES FOR THE INFORM STAKEHOLDER GROUP

Stakeholder Group	Planned Activities	Planned KPIs	Completed activities/ KPIs	Partners involved
Inform	STADIEM website	>1500 unique visitors per month	12900 unique visitors since inception	Martel
	STADIEM promotional videos	4 videos per year 100 views per video	STADIEM channels: 24 videos Total view: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Youtube: >2.200 Twitter & LinkedIn: > 300k impressions Partner channels: VRT: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 5 videos MCB: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 3 videos STK: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> One video All: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reshare project posts on social media 	Martel, VRT, MCB, STK, NMA, F6S, EBU
	Communication on social media, such as LinkedIn and Twitter	Twitter > 300 followers LinkedIn > 100 followers	STADIEM channels: Twitter: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 480 posts - 253 followers 	Martel, VRT, MCB, NMA

			<p>LinkedIn:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • >400 posts • 568 followers <p>Average social media following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 410 stakeholders <p>Partner channels:</p> <p>VRT:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 42 posts on LinkedIn (2025 followers) <p>MCB:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 36 posts and 32 reshares on LinkedIn, Twitter, Facebook, Instagram <p>NMA:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 7 posts on LinkedIn <p>STK:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 4 posts on LinkedIn 	
	Word-to-mouth campaigns during industry-networking events	Not applicable	<p>Consortium members present at Slush 2021, TechChill Milan 2022, Radio Days Europe 2022, Solid World 2022, IBC2022, Future Week 2021 and Future Week 2022</p> <p>see also list of 17 events in convince section 'engage at workshop/events'</p>	Storytek, VRT, MCB, F6S, NMA, EBU

4. CONVINCING

To persuade stakeholders to closely follow the STADIEM project and understand its value, STADIEM has organized various activities and met the necessary performance indicators. These activities include the following:

- Consortium has published 4 press releases
- Consortium partners have contributed to amplifying the project's communication through targeted publications (Tech-I by the EBU or in Sifted for VRT) and reporting on STADIEM in newsletters. A full list of these targeted publications (magazines, newsletters) can be read in Annex III in the Annex section of this deliverable.
- STADIEM has increased its visibility by attending various events, although these events have primarily been hosted by organisations close to the consortium partners due to Covid-19 measures (including Future Media Hubs, Production Technology Seminar, MCB Expo, F6S).
- The focus for the last year of the project is to increase the scope of organisations hosting STADIEM's workshops and events
- STADIEM has organised a campaign to engage corporates in the project.

TABLE 2: OVERVIEW OF THE COMMUNITY BUILDING ACTIVITIES FOR THE CONVINCING STAKEHOLDER GROUP

Stakeholder Group	Planned Activities	Planned KPIs	Completed activities/ KPIs	Partners involved
Convince	Invitations to participate in workshops /events	At least 6 per year	11 events 6 Future Media Hub presentations of STADIEM project and pitching of start-ups MCB Expo 2021 (from 1h:15min) EBU PTS 2022 Walifornia Pitch 2022 Solid World online April 2022 (from min 15' about STADIEM) Techchill 2022 side-event 'Opportunities for Growth' hosted by F6S	MCB, VRT, NMA, STK, NMA, EBU, F6S

	Engage at workshop/ events	At least 6 per year	<p>Attended as presenter or visitor and promoted from that role STADIEM and contribute via networking activities to building the community network at the following 17 events:</p> <p>Venice XR-days (September 2021), International FDCP conference (September 2022), Artech 2021, B3 Biennale Market 2021 (October 2021), Frankfurt Book Fair Innovation KIC conference (October 2021), Startup Speed dating Night (October 2021), Geneva Digital Market (November 2022), InfraChain Summit, Industry@Tallinn & Baltic Event (November 2021), Berlinale & EFM startups 2022, Kinnernord 2022 (March 2022), TTB (April 2022), SXSW online 2022 (March 2022), Marche Du Film (May 2022), Kinnernet Europe (June 2022), Arvamusfestival August 2022), Nordic Flair (September 2022), Radio Days Europe 2022 (April 2022)</p>	STK, VRT
	Targeted publications	Not applicable	<p>STADIEM Project</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> press releases in total since inception : 8 	MARTEL, VRT, MCB, NMA, EBU, F6S, STK

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 5th press release (OC2 launch) distributed to 150 specialised press contacts; • press coverage in 6 publications (including VRT Innovatie; tech-i magazine; Sifted); • Campaign for corporate engagement targeted 5 specialised publications (tvtech, Broadcast, Rapid TV News, TVB Europe, NewscastStudio) and featured in STADIEM's 6th press release (distributed to 47 contacts) <p>Featured articles on external newsletters and internal board of partners</p> <p>VRT:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 4 publications: 2 on public website, 1 internal website and 1 article Sifted <p>MCB:</p>	
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			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website articles and newsletter: 2 dedicated website articles <p>Several items in newsletter</p> <p>NMA:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • articles in newsletter 3 articles in newsletter about OMR 1 article in newsletter about Pilot Phase <p>F6S:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • OC2 announcements in targeted channels in network (platform, social media) <p>EBU:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presentation STADIEM and OC2 promotion in Article Tech-i EBU-Magazine December 2021 <p>STK:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • STADIEM OC1 Pilot case study (September 2022 produced) 	
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5. ENGAGE

To engage the stakeholders that STADIEM would like to be strongly involved in its community, STADIEM has organised, on the one hand, activities targeted at European start-ups and scale-ups and, on the other hand, activities on the European scene and within the hubs that foster exchange and interaction between start-ups and scale-ups participating in the STADIEM Innovation Program and European corporates, investors and other relevant actors. The table below shows that STADIEM, in its 2nd year, met the KPIs and related activities to achieve the goal.

Three challenges were addressed in the 2nd year compared to the previous:

- Increasing the geographical diversity of participants in the open call.
- Organising physical events to integrate the second cohort into the hubs - one by each hub.
- Organising physical events to present STADIEM and showcase the beneficiaries of the program at international conferences

The webinars promoting the STADIEM Innovation Program attracted a larger and more geographically diverse audience, including participants from Eastern and Southern Europe. This is reflected in the increased geographical diversity of applications received for the second open call. More information on the second open call can be read in D3.6 '*Analytics on the submitted proposals OC2*'.

The end of Covid-19 restrictions allowed for the integration of the selected beneficiaries of the second cohort into the network of hubs through physical events at VRT, MCB, and NMA, as well as through travel to other events and corporates within the hub sphere. Additionally, STADIEM organised events at international conferences where beneficiaries from the first and second cohorts could showcase their solutions to a broader audience.

STADIEM had its stand at OMR 2022 (May 2022), its boot at IBC2022 at the MCB stand (September 2022), and boot and side-event at TechChill Milano 2022 at F6S stand. Complementary to these actions, the STADIEM consortium presented the project during the PTS 2022 from EBU and organised the demo-day of open call one during Future Week at MCB.

STADIEM also engaged media corporates, innovators, and start-ups/scale-ups in eight project-related events, including online pitching and presentation of start-ups to corporates and participation of start-ups at events of partners/actors related to STADIEM consortium partners. For example, two STADIEM beneficiaries from the Match OC2 phase participated in the FMH event at Media City Odense in June 2022.

The participation of STADIEM members in events and the events organised by STADIEM was promoted through STADIEM's communication channels (website and social media) and the (online/social) networks of Martel and other STADIEM partners. Promotional materials, such as pod design, videos, and brochures, were produced to support the engagement of stakeholders during these events.

TABLE 3: OVERVIEW OF THE COMMUNITY BUILDING ACTIVITIES FOR THE ENGAGE STAKEHOLDER GROUP

Stakeholder Group	Planned Activities	Planned KPIs	Completed activities/ KPIs	Partners involved
Engage	Webinars to promote the programme	2 per open call	2 webinars 90+70 participants (Jan 28 + Feb 10 2022) Participation from all partners	F6S, VRT & Martel (lead), NMA, STK, MCB, EBU
	Showcasing and getting together at international events facilitated by the STADIEM network	Not applicable	7 events: WebSummit 2021, <u>Slush 2021</u> (side event, hosted by STK), PTS 2022 OMR 2022, IBC 2022, TechChill Milano 2022,	STK, NMA, MCB, VRT, EBU, F6S
	Showcasing and getting together at international events organised by the STADIEM network	Not applicable	1 event: Future Week 2022	MCB
	Big Bang proceeding the Match Phase of OC2	1 event	1 event on 2nd May 2022	NMA, MCB (lead), STK, VRT, NMA, Martel, EBU, F6S
	Develop Phase Onboarding OC2	Not applicable	1st August 2022	VRT (lead), MCB, NMA, STK
	Participation in project-related events	At least 4	8 events Sandbox Hub Challenges - November 2021 NMA Demo Day 12 October 2021	VRT, F6S, NMA, STK

			<p>OC1 Integration Phase event - panel with international tech experts on Integration - March 2022</p> <p>Pitch Sandbox Hub May 2022</p> <p>Media City Odense 2022 - June 2022</p> <p>Wallifornia 2022 - June 2022</p> <p>Network events Tech Chill Milano - F6S - Sept 2022</p> <p>Happy Hour at IBC 2022 - Sept 2022</p>	
	Demo Day at the end of the project	1 Demo Day per open call	Future Week demo day event 2022	MCB
	Access to and integration in the partner's hub and networks	Not applicable	<p>4 events/2 activitis</p> <p>Match OC2 hub events</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Innovation cafés VRT Sandbox – VRT • OMR boot and matchmaking – NMA • Future Week 2022 - MCB • OC2 Investor and Corporate Match 	VRT, MCB, NMA, STK, F6S

			<p>week - STK</p> <p>Cohort Match OC2 - Travel to events and corporates for lead generation and LOI within sphere of hubs</p> <p>Regular (bi- monthly) update of STADIEM Progress for each phase in OC1/OC in the Sandbox Hub</p>	
	Videos, interview and success stories online	Not applicable	See testimonials; MCB expo	

6. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE PERSPECTIVE

Conclusion

This deliverable presented that STADIEM achieved or exceeded all of its key performance indicators (KPIs) for community building in the period from October 2021 to September 2022. The deliverable thus presented the overview of the project's communication and engagement strategy and then proceeded to list key achievements that were grouped according to the: Inform, Convince, Engage methodology.

One major difference from the previous year was the impact of the easing of Covid-19 restrictions in the European Union. This allowed STADIEM to increase its physical presence at events such as conferences, conventions, and workshops, and to reach out to various stakeholder groups in its ecosystem.

The return of in-person events was particularly beneficial for the 40 beneficiaries selected in the second open call, as they were able to travel to hubs and meet with corporate partners to secure letters of intent for their development proposals.

STADIEM also had the opportunity to showcase the beneficiaries of its first and second open calls to a wider audience of media stakeholders at events like Future Week, IBC, Media City Odense, and Tech Chill Milano. In addition, STADIEM consortium members were able to focus on conveying information and engaging with stakeholder groups in person, in addition to online activities.

A look into the future.

In the first two years of the project, STADIEM focused on building its ecosystem and encouraging media companies and corporates to participate in the STADIEM Innovation Program through the open call process. In the final year of the project, STADIEM will shift its focus to showcasing the results and lessons learned from the program, highlighting success stories, and connecting the beneficiaries with relevant stakeholders and audiences to support their continued development after the end of EU funding. STADIEM will continue to use the KPIs defined in its initial community building plan, but the specific events, publications, and social media activities will be tailored to the need to connect with stakeholders that are important for the sustainability of the project.

The main challenges for the final year of the project are the following.

To support the sustainability of the project after September 2023, STADIEM plans to:

- Organize 3 workshops focused on particular stakeholders to present insights and lessons from the second year of the project and highlight success stories.
- Set up events and activities to connect STADIEM beneficiaries with relevant actors in the broader ecosystem to support their growth and development.
- Find and secure a suitable opportunity for the final demo day for the 4 STADIEM OC2 pilots.
- Develop a strategy for post-project ecosystem engagement and for directing the project's efforts after the end of EU funding.

ANNEXES

ANNEX I: OVERVIEW OF VIDEOS BY PROJECT AND PARTNERS

Project Videos

Partner	date	Titel	Views (youtube)	link
Martel	19/10/2021	STADIEM's First Consortium Meeting and Pitching Event @ Future Week	59	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=VkkTi1tOr2U
Martel	1/11/2021	STADIEM's Open Call 1 - A few words from the hubs - VRT	119	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=4euulP95Tf4
Martel	22/11/2021	STADIEM's Open Call 1: A few words from the Hubs - Media City Bergen	41	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=nh9ZAVtjtc8
Martel	26/11/2021	STADIEM - Piloting and acceleration programme (Version 2):	429	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=w5qO6xm9wWE
Martel	8/12/2021	STADIEM's Open call 1: A few words from the Hubs - Storytek	11	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=yZ8U8k6mpKE
Martel	09/12/2021	EU-funding for 40 B2B start-ups in MediaTech: STADIEM at SLUSH	46	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ptn8H2CXuRc
Martel	10/12/2021	STADIEM at MCB Expo	11	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=5tItaVm_nMw
Martel	16/12/2021	STADIEM's Open Call 1: A few words from the Hubs - NMA	101	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=5tItaVm_nMw

Martel	31/01/2022	STADIEM Open call 2 webinar #1	89	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Qo_yUK3chu4
Martel	13/01/2022	STADIEM's OPEN CALL 1: A few words from the Scale- ups - FanSifter	98	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=RWcd5t7YU-4
Martel	19/01/2022	STADIEM's OPEN CALL 1: A few words from the Scale- ups Aiconix	63	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=5Fhm0eUPqwE
Martel	25/01/2022	STADIEM's OPEN CALL 1: A few words from the Scale- ups - Datavillage	87	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=9bUDw3VPKcw
Martel	25/01/2022	STADIEM's OPEN CALL 1: A few words from the Scale- ups - The Chainless / DeepVA:	67	
Martel	28/01/2022	STADIEM's OPEN CALL 1: A few words from the Scale- ups - Frameright: 69	69	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=0xtrX2unAUl
Martel	28/01/2022	STADIEM's OPEN CALL 1: A few words from the Scale- ups - Nowtilus: 86	86	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=1dKYp1RHXgM
Martel	02/03/2022	STADIEM's OPEN CALL 1: A few words from the Scale- ups - Zazu	81	https://youtu.be/wXNM9qmb08Q
Martel	04/03/2022	STADIEM's OPEN CALL 1: A few words from the Scale- ups - Visualyst	58	https://youtu.be/JGGMfMc68QA
Martel	31/01/2022	STADIEM Open Call 2	88	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Qo_yUK3chu4

		webinar #1 - Full recording		
Martel	11/02/2022	STADIEM Open Call 2 webinar #2 - Full recording: 105	105	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=tnF2A6JKYLS

An additional clip to promote Open Call 2 webinars was created but posted exclusively on social media to be used in the related paid adv campaign (total reach: >220k)

Videos VRT

Partner	date	Titel	Views (LinkedIn)	link
VRT - Sandbox	May 2022	Matchmaking event at VRT	887	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6940204575811358720/
VRT - Sandbox	August 2022	Druid learning - Introduction Develop Phase with Corporate VRT	887	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6963118228319412224
VRT - Sandbox	August 2022	Wantent - Introduction Develop Phase with Corporate VRT	209	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6962438747300732928
VRT - Sandbox	August 2022	Limecraft - Introduction Develop Phase with Corporate VRT	985	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6960235922072215552/
VRT - Sandbox	August 2022	BotTalk - Introduction Develop Phase with Corporate VRT	321	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6960553140735614976/

MCB Videos

Partner	date	Titel	Views (LinkedIn)	link
MCB	07/10/2022	STADIEM Pitching Contest at Future Week 2021	43	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=fXT-sLOd2Xq&list=PLmOhsyHij8ALNqFyn1BqLhivWpNwrkV2i&index=18&t=2452s
MCB	03/12/2021	Presentation STADIEM at MCB Expo (online alternative to cancelled IBC 2021 presence)	267	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=F5lZUkpZSZg
MCB	27/06/2022	STADIEM demo presentation Accelerating Next-Generation Media Tech Innovations at Future Week 2022	38	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=8oV_xJFZYjI&list=PLmOhsyHij8AL2E_7WbJKcNZFrMF_KzG6T&index=9&t=1591s

ANNEX II : COMMUNICATION ON SOCIAL MEDIA

Besides the 400 posts on Twitter and LinkedIn on the STADIEM project social media and curated by communication partner Martel, the 4 hubs have actively communicated on social media about STADIEM via their social media channels.

VRT

VRT Sandbox posted on its LinkedIn Account (2100 followers) 42 posts regarding diverse elements of the Project.

Partner	date	Titel	link
VRT-Sandbox	29/10/2021	Future week 2021	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6859782019652567040
VRT-Sandbox	4/11/2021	OC1: VRT	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6862002341575446528

VRT-Sandbox	25/11/2021	STADIEM @ Slush: European Mediatech networking event	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6869602575797256192
VRT-Sandbox	26/11/2021	OC1: MCB	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6869922497605722113
VRT-Sandbox	1/12/2021	OC2: announcement	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6871781304812367872
VRT-Sandbox	2/12/2021	STADIEM @ MCB online expo	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6872200751427526657
VRT-Sandbox	6/12/2021	STADIEM @ EBU itech	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6873563775690264576
VRT - Sandbox	13/12/2021	Anneke Gyzen	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6876168436314120192
VRT - Sandbox	15/12/2021	Launch OC2	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6876853719430942720
VRT - Sandbox	21/12/2021	OC1 case: Tinkerlist	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6879036420476977152
VRT - Sandbox	28/12/2021	OC1 case: Datavillage	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6881500968412872704
VRT - Sandbox	31/12/2021	STADIEM year overview 2021	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6882591253846913024
VRT - Sandbox	4/01/2022	OC1 case: Ceretai	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6884037647434612736
VRT - Sandbox	6/01/2022	OC1 case: Smartocto	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6884826378932428800
VRT - Sandbox	17/01/2022	OC1 case: FanSifter	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6888850137846706176
VRT - Sandbox	25/01/2022	Benefits OC2 (webinar)	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6891726435846090753

VRT - Sandbox	27/01/2022	OC2: Content is King	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6892398003261685760
VRT - Sandbox	03/02/2022	OC2: Data	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6894923128490065921
VRT - Sandbox	10/02/2022	OC2: Monetization	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6897529177374109696
VRT - Sandbox	17/02/2022	OC2: Archiving	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6900004503656001537
VRT - Sandbox	22/02/2022	OC2 Video: time is ticking	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6901817158980943873
VRT - Sandbox	24/02/2022	OC2: reminder	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6902549898626248704
VRT - Sandbox	16/03/2022	OC1: start integrate phase	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6909864710184050689
VRT - Sandbox	17/03/2022	Datavillage in the house	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6910196701324546049
VRT - Sandbox	24/03/2022	OC1: selection integrate phase	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6912683486201942016
VRT - Sandbox	29/03/2022	OC1: Tinkerlist usecase	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6914561335867412480
VRT - Sandbox	11/04/2022	Event: Solid World: Datavillage	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6919257466987802624
VRT - Sandbox	24/03/2022	OC1: selection integrate phase	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6912683486201942016
VRT - Sandbox	14/04/2022	OC1: usecase Web64	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6920277682094018560
VRT - Sandbox	03/05/2022	OC2: match phase: welcome	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6927218472288464896
VRT - Sandbox	11/05/2022	OC2: welcome at VRT hub	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:69301197224452464
VRT - Sandbox	13/05/2022	OC2: welcome at VRT hub post 2	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6930827981711917056
VRT - Sandbox	16/05/2022	Event: Radiodays Europe: RTBF & Datavillage	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6931911940868861953

VRT - Sandbox	24/05/2022	Press : Sifted	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6934795241203888128
VRT - Sandbox	01/06/2022	OC2: pilot phase: 4 VRT cases	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6937695665858723841
VRT - Sandbox	08/06/2022	OC2: match phase: VRT hub	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6940204575811358720
VRT - Sandbox	22/06/2022	OC1: Tinkerlist by Future Media Hubs	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6945330834354675712
VRT - Sandbox	02/08/2022	OC2: Limecraft video	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6960235922072215552
VRT - Sandbox	03/08/2022	OC2: Bottalk video	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6960553140735614976
VRT - Sandbox	08/08/2022	OC2: Wantent video	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6962438747300732928
VRT - Sandbox	10/08/2022	OC2: Druid Learning video	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6963118228319412224
VRT - Sandbox	02/09/2022	STADIEM @ IBC	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6971380662293385216
VRT - Sandbox	12/09/2022	STADIEM @ IBC: happy hour	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6975032325130575872

MCB

Over its various social media accounts (LinkedIn, Twitter, Facebook, Instagram), MCB has posted 36 messages including reposts

Partner	date	Titel	link
MCB	2/11/21	Open Call Opportunities	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6861264739557765120
MCB	11/11/21	IBC stand 2021	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6864546951325618176
MCB	11/11/21	IBC presence 2021	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6864865493904318464
MCB	19/11/21	SLUSH 2021	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6867399155447279616

MCB	22/11/21	Stay Tuned for OC2	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6868472108574367744
MCB	29/11/21	Mcb Expo	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6871092399964229632
MCB	01/12/21	OC2	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6871795913195569152
MCB	08/12/21	OC2	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6874267618342137857
MCB	13/12/21	MCB Expo	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6876074803107913728
MCB	15/12/21	OC 2	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6876852078237618176
MCB	20/12/21	OC2	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6878689779404328960
MCB	12/01/22	OC2	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6886999923707928576
MCB	19/01/22	Webinar	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6889477277432745984
MCB	28/01/22	Webinar	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6892812901019983872
MCB	21/02/22	OC2	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6901616558259732480
MCB	28/02/22	OC2	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6903986580739227648
MCB	05/09/2022	IBC 2022	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6972555956362600449
MCB	09/09/2022	IBC 2022	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6973973754422931456
MCB	19/10/21	Future Week 21	https://twitter.com/MediaCityBergen/status/1450462222585634840?s=20&t=gzKOFsSwd_BwiiLZz2BDag
MCB	20/12/21	OC2	https://twitter.com/MediaCityBergen/status/1472917526963277827?s=20&t=gzKOFsSwd_BwiiLZz2BDag

MCB	25/01/22	OC2	https://twitter.com/MediaCityBergen/status/1485990630304235520?s=20&t=gzKOFsSwd_BwiiLZz2BDag
MCB	28/01/2022	Webinar	https://twitter.com/MediaCityBergen/status/1487036305624162304?s=20&t=gzKOFsSwd_BwiiLZz2BDag
MCB	21/02/22	OC2	https://twitter.com/MediaCityBergen/status/1495851772400877581?s=20&t=gzKOFsSwd_BwiiLZz2BDag
MCB	28/02/22	OC2	https://twitter.com/MediaCityBergen/status/1498221490126348289?s=20&t=gzKOFsSwd_BwiiLZz2BDag
MCB	03/06/2022	Pilot phase	https://twitter.com/MediaCityBergen/status/1532683199389769728?s=20&t=gzKOFsSwd_BwiiLZz2BDag
MCB	30/11/2021	MCB Expo	https://www.instagram.com/p/CW5DrmsKK3V/?utm_source=ig_web_copy_link
MCB	13/12/21	MCB Expo	https://www.instagram.com/p/CXa8WLBmWWP/?utm_source=ig_web_copy_link
MCB	20/12/21	OC2	https://www.instagram.com/p/CXtO-JKoeHP/?utm_source=ig_web_copy_link
MCB	21/02/22	OC2	https://www.instagram.com/tv/CaQltHhD37t/?utm_source=ig_web_copy_link
MCB	09/09/22	IBC 2022	https://www.instagram.com/p/CiR2pK_M4Nk/?utm_source=ig_web_copy_link
MCB	19/11/21	Slush	pfbid02r6MowW6cMQ6GBCsxnRcq4wEdqZ619HxUCJJAxnzhTsY5rFQR7SJr8rZ7KugJBiJxl
MCB	29/11/21	MCB Expo	pfbid0292hsjiqYU9EqNiCCNRKy pjU2XxuwNB1fT82eFEgqiuGRGhuXFSAHhqpYUHPNVyYfl
MCB	13/12/2021	MCB Expo	pfbid02ZXdwYQ47eayvaAAyCFrhGqXv61a8NjFsZn9HWxV2Pzm9ppaac6dzRWRHpxQaj56l
MCB	20/12/21	OC2	pfbid0hzyY7f9ReomjLNvdsBqpuXtVDG6w48Hxp1KgLHVdY66VERq4MpZVRoUiFK5XLSjl
MCB	28/02/21	OC2	pfbid02FNxkZ7oaw4svTXNLmErjN8w1a5vQYWW6e2BZBqTupicNMVupEnhDL8peFtRsC3yWI

MCB	09/09/22	IBC	pfbid0AMbChd53UTkFwYFnjWjr uiaibNn2PAcA422uBs36L5H9qb p4febF25ZGJPhsv48Wl
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NMA

NMA posted on its LinkedIn channel actively around the OMR event and the Match Phase event in Hamburg in May 2022

Partner	date	Titel	link
NMA	May 2022	OMR 2022	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6930077595363364865
NMA	May 2022	OMR 2022	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6930452492434436096
NMA	May 2022	OMR 2022	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6931948217903239168
NMA	May 2022	OMR 2022	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6932296005090488320
NMA	May 2022	OMR 2022	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6932366470257549313
NMA	May 2022	OMR 2022	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6932571893749186560
NMA	May 2022	OMR 2022	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6933072177999069185
NMA	June 2022	Pilot Phase	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6937744530448257025

STORYTEK

Storytek communicated via its LinkedIn Channel (3484 followers) 4x times specific on STADIEM activities with its own content creation, besides resharing Stadiem social media project posts.

Partner	date	Titel	link
STK	January 2022	STADIEM OC2 and tech-i publication STADIEM	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/stensaluve_er_stadiem-startup-mediatech-activity-6873558958989209600-4zpU/?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
STK	February 2022	STADIEM Open Call 2 promotion	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/stensaluve_er_opencall-mediainnovations-incubation-activity-6904062436844933120-goYC/?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
STK	June 2022	STADIEM OC2 Promo for Corporate and Investor matches	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/stensaluve_er_activity-6939990373763092480-plxC/?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
STK	September 2022	OC1 Pilot Case Study: Filmchain	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/stensaluve_er_horizoneurope-innovation-startups-activity-7003686274003791872-

			2DK /?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
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ANNEX III: TARGETED PUBLICATIONS OF STADIEM

Besides the press releases issued by communication Martel and the targeted campaigns by Martel to corporates, the STADIEM partners realised the following articles in (online) magazines and external/internal newsletters:

Partner	date	Titel	link
VRT	01/09/2021	Article on vrt.be: VRT and European scale-ups build future media solutions through innovative piloting program -	https://www.vrt.be/en/over-de-vrt/news/2021/08/31/vrt-and-european-scale-ups-build-future-media-solutions-through/
VRT	15/09/2021	Article on vrt.be: STADIEM doet open oproep aan start-ups en scale-ups	https://www.vrt.be/nl/over-de-vrt/nieuws/2021/12/15/stadiem-doet-open-oproep-aan-start-ups-en-scale-ups/
VRT	29/09/2022	Article on August (internal VRT news site)	Ken je Gamescom en IBC? VRT Innovatie was aanwezig
VRT	24/05/2022	Article on Sifted: How the Flemish public broadcaster VRT became a media innovation powerhouse (referring to STADIEM)	https://sifted.eu/articles/vrt-sandbox-media-venture-fund
EBU	10/02/2022	Article in Tech-I issue 50: Calling innovators to enhance Europe's Next Generation Media Ecosystem	https://tech.ebu.ch/news/2021/12/stadiem-calling-innovators-to-enhance-europes-next-generation-media-ecosystem
MCB	October 2021 - September 2022	- Several features on the Media City Bergen Newsletter	
MCB	20/12/21	OC2 Announcement at MCB website	https://mediacitybergen.no/home/stadiem-oc2/
MCB	03/05/2022	Match Phase start-ups announced on Media City Bergen website	https://mediacitybergen.no/home/stadiem-match-oc2/
NMA	May 2022	OMR	https://us11.campaign-archive.com/?u=cf573fd2a58ebedd25f2a5ca6&id=7763ef9a90
NMA	May 2022	OMR	https://us11.campaign-archive.com/?u=cf573fd2a58ebedd25f2a5ca6&id=49272fba62
NMA	May 2022	OMR	https://us11.campaign-archive.com/?u=cf573fd2a58ebedd25f2a5ca6&id=9b50488e98
F6S	January-February 2022	Open Call 2	Social media posts and newsletter

STK	September 2022	STADIEM OC1 Pilot Case study Filmchain	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/stensaluveer_horizoneurope-innovation-startups-activity-7003686274003791872-2DK/?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
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